

GIG ECONOMY, STRENGTHENING HUMAN RESOURCES AND DIGITAL COMMUNICATION STRATEGIES TOWARDS DECENT WORK IN SUPPORTING SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT (SDGs 8) IN MATARAM CITY

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Abstract

GIG Economy have new flexible job opportunities especially for women who have dual responsibilities in society. This study aims to examine the influence of the GIG Economy, Human Resource Development, and Digital Communication Strategy on Decent Work in Supporting Sustainable Development (SDGs 8) in Mataram City. Using a sample of 100 female workers respondents who work in the digitalization sector (remote working). The independent variables are the GIG Economy, Human Resource Development, and Digital Communication Strategy with the dependent variable being Decent Work. This type of causal quantitative research uses multiple linear regression analysis as the data processing method. The sampling method is purposive sampling with accidental sampling as the sampling technique. The data collection method uses a questionnaire. The research instrument is tested with validity and reliability tests. Before analyzing the research data, a classical assumption test is first carried out, followed by a t-test and an F-test for drawing conclusions. The results of the study state that the GIG Economy, Human Resource Development, and Digital Communication Strategy have a positive and significant effect, both partially and simultaneously, on Decent Work. This means that job opportunities through the GIG Economy, improving the quality of skills and abilities in utilizing digital platforms collectively become an effective strategy in encouraging the realization of decent work for female workers and directly supporting the successful achievement of SDGs 8 in Mataram City.

Keywords: *GIG Economy, Human Resource Development, Digital Communication Strategy, Decent Work, SDGs8.*

INTRODUCTION

Current technological developments present both opportunities and potential aspects that can be utilized and leveraged by the public and government to support sustainable development. One example is the emergence of the GIG Economy, which provides access for all levels of society to improve well-being. The GIG Economy is able to leverage a free-flowing work system by leveraging various digital platforms without compromising on desired output targets. (Kamarudin & Arif, 2024) The development of the digital world has opened up wider job opportunities, making the exchange of services and trade of products easier. However, other things to consider include the uncertainty of time and increasingly competitive competition. The GIG Economy is not yet able to guarantee a fixed income for workers. The GIG Economy focuses on preparing a workforce with skills and expertise related to digitalization technology, such as communication skills, adapting to new work models, improving adequate digital infrastructure, technology education, and digital financial literacy. (Amory et al., 2025). The development of increasingly better technology utilization can boost the productivity of work performed, thereby impacting organizational profits. Strengthening human resources to develop the competencies and skills to apply various digital platforms is a challenge in itself to achieving comprehensive well-being. This empowerment will produce a workforce with high productivity and efficiency, as well as competitiveness in their fields, thus positively supporting company competitiveness and economic growth. Strengthening human resources can create an empowered society,

foster sustainable progress, and become agents of change by disseminating knowledge and skills, which can be achieved through various aspects, including knowledge, skills, attitude change, and education. (NLA Putri et al., 2025) Access to information and learning through both formal and non-formal education can hone people's skills in solving problems and finding alternative solutions. Human Capital Theory states that humans, or employees, are vital assets that can improve organizational performance. Investments in human resources can increase the productivity and efficiency of an organization as a whole. (Ahyar et al., 2020) In the digital era, the development and strengthening of human resources is related to social cognitive theory, where a person's skills can be improved through social interaction, observation and direct experience that can be obtained in the world of work that is directly related to the use of technology. (Heryana et al., 2023).

Through digital platforms, such as social media, job search sites and AI-based applications, as well as other supporting applications, women can get job opportunities that match their skills. (Duffy & Schwartz, 2018) Optimizing digital communication enables the rapid, transparent, and inclusive dissemination of information that can increase employment opportunities and raise awareness of women workers' rights, such as equal pay or wages, workplace protection, and maternity leave rights. (Heryana et al., 2023). Although, there are many benefits offered in implementing a digital communication strategy, there are still several challenges that need to be overcome, such as the gap in technology access between men and women that occurs in developing countries. (Heryana et al., 2023) Therefore, digital technology has become a platform for the development of flexible work models such as remote working and the gig economy, which provide benefits for female workers who also have family responsibilities. (Heryana et al., 2023). Thus, this provides many options and opportunities for female workers to remain productive without having to sacrifice their domestic roles.

Indonesia is determined to implement the 2030 achievement plan in line with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by emphasizing support for Human Rights, reducing poverty, addressing injustice and paying full attention to the implications of social and economic improvement and ecosystem protection, which of course requires the role of human resources in development to increase growth. (NM Putri et al., 2024) The three pillars used as indicators in the development of SDGs are firstly human development in the form of education and health, secondly socio-economic development such as the provision of environmental facilities and infrastructure and economic growth and thirdly environmental development such as the availability of natural resources and good environmental quality. (Nurgiyanti et al., 2022).

One of the SDGs goals related to economic well-being is goal 8, namely regarding decent work and economic growth. (Ponto, 2023). The presence of GIG Economy in the economy that provides flexibility for part-time freelance workers to work flexibly and independently as well as support for human resource strengthening competencies for the fulfillment and use of digitalization media to be able to conduct business interactions online is part of community activities that can support the implementation of sustainable development in sector 8 which has an impact on economic growth. This study aims to determine the effect of GIG Economy, Human Resource Strengthening and Digital Communication Strategy on Decent Work in Supporting Sustainable Development in Mataram City which focuses on female workers who have double demands (double burden) in society both as workers and family members who take care of the household, children and partners as well as female workers who are pursuing further education. Working women who bear a double burden have a deep responsibility for individuals, families, and society as a whole. The existence of the GIG Economy (part-time economy) is one of the flexible and innovative solutions to improve women's welfare, promote equality, and ultimately support inclusive and sustainable economic growth supported by aspects of human resource strengthening that can be a tool for empowering relevant training to increase women's competitiveness in the job market and digital communication that allows women to work more efficiently, connect with communities, and even build professional networks without having to sacrifice family time.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The presence of the GIG Economy encourages the opening of employment opportunities that can be utilized by every individual to improve the quality of life. The phenomenon of the presence of the GIG Economy by recruiting a variety of workers in the form of independent contracts through digital platforms is becoming increasingly popular in the current labor market. The GIG Economy is an economic system where work is carried out on the basis of short projects, temporary contracts or specific tasks, rather than in the form of stable permanent employment. Workers are usually known as GIG workers or freelancers and generally work for various clients or companies by utilizing digital platforms such as applications or websites that bring them together with job opportunities. (Faqih, 2024). A new form of economy where income has a positive impact on the workforce's decision to work in the GIG Economy, where the policies implemented by each company will have a major impact on GIG Workers such as wage levels and

minimum working hours, company operational standards, and restrictions on the acceptance of workers who work in the GIG Economy.(Prestianawati et al., 2023). Based on the Theory of Planned Behavior, there are 3 components that are the main focus that must be considered regarding the GIG Economy, including:(Darsono et al., 2020)namely attitude toward the behavior, namely the extent to which a person has a positive or negative assessment of a behavior, subjective norms are an individual's perception of social pressure to do or not do a behavior and perceived behavioral control is an individual's perception of the ease or difficulty in doing an action, similar to the concept of self-efficacy.

Quantitative research using Partial Least Square-Structural Equation Modeling data analysis techniques examines the creative economy sector that contributes to national domestic products and obtains results, job challenges have a negative and significant effect on the success of GIG actors, job autonomy does not have a significant effect on the success of GIG workers, individual intellectual capital has a positive and significant effect on the success of GIG workers, individual intellectual capital as a moderating variable influences the relationship between job challenges and the success of GIG workers, and individual intellectual capital as a moderating variable does not influence the relationship between job autonomy and the success of GIG workers.(Wendra & Besari, 2023).

Analytical observational research using a case-control research design on GIG Economy Workers found that there is an important role of the Digital Freelancer marketplace in the development of GIG Economy Workers. This has an impact on increasing the number of GIG Economy workers and social media plays a big role and is one of the tools that can be used by workers in terms of increasing income, or doing promotions on social media so as to encourage increased income for GIG economy workers. It can be said that social media is a contributor to the development of GIG Economy Workers.(Masakazu et al., 2023).

Study(Masakazu et al., 2023)focuses on the challenges of the GIG Economy in the SDGs. The study focused on retail trade and food sales, namely Swiggy and Zomato, and the transportation sector, namely Ola and Uber. Primary data was used by distributing questionnaires to a sample of GIG workers in the city of Pune, Maharashtra, India. The sample used was 200 respondents. The analysis used descriptive statistics by analyzing the responses from respondents. The results found(Masakazu et al., 2023)The challenges faced by GIG workers in India vary. The GIG economy in India provides accident insurance to workers but not other forms of insurance, such as health insurance, sick leave, and so on. In terms of education, companies have made no efforts to develop employees, particularly in terms of improving their education and skills. GIG workers, who are freelancers, in reality work 7 hours a day to earn a decent income, and there are no career development prospects, such as promotions and equal pay.

Theodore Schultz's theory of human capital suggests that the best investment lies in human resources, focusing on education. Well-educated human resources, the focus of a nation's development, can directly contribute to its economic growth. Positive economic growth can be achieved by providing education, improving skills and expertise, and increasing workforce productivity.(Wujarso, 2022). In human capital theory, two approaches are used: the Nelson-Phelps approach (1966), which states that human capital is an important factor that can increase a country's economic growth, and the Lucas approach (1988), which focuses on two factors regarding human capital, where a country's economic growth emphasizes human capital that focuses on education and learning by doing. At the macro or corporate level, the implementation of green HR functions (such as altruism, empathy, and environmentally friendly attitudes) and the formation of a transparent organizational culture can increase the possibility of achieving SDGs 8 (decent work and economic growth) and can reduce inequality in the workplace. Meanwhile, at the international level, it was found that globalization factors can encourage the growth of a paradigm of integrated and environmentally friendly social practices facilitated by companies. In developed and developing countries, these practices have a positive impact on social achievement and financial performance. Other findings also indicate the need for environmentally friendly training to produce environmentally friendly competencies in human resources, which can ultimately facilitate the implementation of SDGs 8, which, if carried out sustainably, can be used to achieve SDGs 12.(Chams & Garcia-Blandón, 2019).

Based on the theory of integrated marketing communications *Integrated Marketing Communication*(IMC) (Belch & Belch, 2004)is a process that integrates various forms of communication to convey or channel messages that are organized, consistent and have persuasive goals to the audience, this strategy provides the possibility for each individual or organization to convey decent work values, such as the right to appropriate and fair wages, social protection and equal employment opportunities through various digital channels effectively. This is also supported by the results of research conducted by(Gunawan & Harliantara, 2023)which states that digital communication strategies are based on *Integrated Marketing Communication*(IMC) can improve image and audience engagement. Research(Ramadhani, 2020)stated that the use of strategies such as media, instructional design strategies, marketing strategies, and participation strategies have proven effective in engaging audiences and providing information to the public in the SDGs development process. Subsequent research on communication strategies is based on the media

used (media-based strategy) in implementing Nawacita and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by the Bojonegoro Regency Government.(Ramadhani, 2020)The research results show that the Bojonegoro Regency Government uses strategies such as media, instructional design strategies, marketing strategies, and participation strategies that have proven effective in engaging the Bojonegoro community while providing information to the public in the development process based on the Nawacita and SDGs values. This indicates that communication strategies can effectively improve sustainable development.

One of the factors that is a focus in the economic sector to support sustainable development is the provision of jobs to reduce unemployment, which is not only about the number of available jobs but also the quality of the jobs offered, because this can help workers develop, respect human rights, and provide sufficient wages for a decent living. There are four basic principles that support decent work.(Ginting et al., 2025)namely rights at work related to decent work that guarantees workers' rights including equality, freedom, security, and human dignity, full and productive employment, namely work that can generate sufficient income to meet the basic needs of workers and their families, social protection, namely workers receive protection against economic risks such as job loss, discrimination based on gender, age, or ethnicity, as well as work accidents or illnesses and social dialogue, namely having the opportunity to dialogue or negotiate between the government, employers, and workers to resolve problems, create social justice, and make policies that benefit all parties.

Hypothesis Development

A new form of economy where income has a positive impact on the workforce's decision to work in the GIG Economy, where the policies implemented by each company will have a major impact on GIG Workers, such as wage levels and minimum working hours, company operational standards, and restrictions on the acceptance of workers who work in the GIG Economy.(Prestianawati et al., 2023)

H1: GIG Economy has a partial effect on Decent Work for female workers in supporting SDGs 8 in Mataram City

Research on human capital(Belch & Belch, 2004)found that human resources can play an important role in achieving sustainable development goals through collaborative actions of stakeholders.

H2: Strengthening of human resources is suspected to have a partial influence on Decent Work for female workers in supporting SDGs 8 in Mataram City.

Research conducted by(Gunawan & Harliantara, 2023)which states that digital communication strategies are based on*Integrated Marketing Communication*(IMC) can improve image and audience engagement. As well as research from(Ramadhani, 2020)which states that the use of strategies such as media, instructional design strategies, marketing strategies, and participation strategies has proven effective in engaging the audience and providing information to the public in the SDGs development process.

H3: Digital Communication Strategy is suspected to have a partial influence on Decent Work for female workers in supporting SDGs 8 in Mataram City.

Research shows that individual intellectual capital plays a significant role in the success of GIG Economy workers.(Wendra & Besari, 2023), meanwhile research from(Masakazu et al., 2023)which emphasizes the importance of digital platforms such as social media in increasing the income of GIG workers. Therefore, in the context of decent work, communication strategies play a role in increasing job opportunities and access to information, especially for women in the informal sector, such as remote working. In addition,(Chams & Garcia-Blandón, 2019)stated that strengthening sustainable human resources, through training and development based on social and environmental values, supports the achievement of SDGs 8.

H4: GIG Economy, Human Resource Strengthening and Digital Communication Strategy are suspected to have a simultaneous influence on Decent Work for female workers in supporting SDGs 8 in Mataram City.

Based on the explanation above, the conceptual framework in this research can be described as follows.

METHOD

The research design was carried out in accordance with scientific research procedures that begin with the existence of an interesting phenomenon that can be used as study material starting from the formulation of hypotheses and quantitative data collection, conducting hypothesis testing, quantitative data analysis, analyzing quantitative test results and drawing conclusions. This research was compiled over a period of six months, starting from the process of preparing a research proposal, data collection, testing and analyzing data and concluding the research results. This type of research is causal quantitative research with instrument development. The model in this study focuses on the relationship framework between independent variables, namely the GIG Economy, Human Resource Strengthening and Digital Communication Strategy with the dependent variable, namely Decent Work in Supporting Sustainable Development (SDGS 8). The location of the research was carried out in Mataram City. Data in the study came from primary data collected directly by distributing questionnaires to respondents who were used as research samples. The population in this study was all female workers in Mataram City using a purposive sampling method with the criteria of female gender and residents of Mataram City, women who work with a minimum age of 15 years and have worked or are currently working in the field of remote working. or work using digital media. To determine a representative sample size for the population, this study used the Slovin formula with a 10% margin of error. This is based on the known population size of 165,749 females aged 15 years and above in Mataram City in 2024. The sampling technique used in this study was accidental sampling. The calculation of the sample size, based on the Slovin formula according to Sugiyono with a 10% margin of error, is as follows:(Majdina et al., 2024):

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Information :

n = Sample size/ number of respondents

N = Population size

e = Margin of error 0.1 (10%)

$$n = \frac{165.749}{1 + 165.749(0,1)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{165.749}{1 + 165.749(0,01)}$$

$$n = \frac{165.749}{1 + 1.657,49}$$

$$n = \frac{165.749}{1.658,49}$$

$$n = 99.94$$

The calculation above yields a sample size of 99.94, rounded to 100, representing the total number of female workers in Mataram City. The data analysis technique used the Classical Assumption Test (Multicollinearity, Autocorrelation, Heteroscedasticity, and Normality). Hypothesis testing was performed using the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) test using SPSS 25. Therefore, the regression equation in this study is:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1X_1+ \beta_2X_2+ \beta_3X_3+ \epsilon$$

Y = Decent Work

X1 = GIG Economy

X2 = Human Resources Strengthening
 X3 = Digital Communication Strategy
 α = Constant
 $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ = Regression Coefficients
 ε = Error

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following validity test uses a significance level of 5% (0.05) with a frequency distribution of $Df = n - 2 = 100 - 2 = 98$ so the r-table value at a df value of 98 is 0.197. The criteria for drawing conclusions about validity are that data is said to be significant if the significance value is less than 0.05 or r-count > r-table. Conversely, data is said to be invalid if the significance value is more than 0.05 or r-count < r-table.

Variables	Question Items	Validity		
		Pearson Correlation	r-table	Sig.
<i>Gig Economy</i> (X1)	X1.1	0.699	0.197	0,000
	X1.2	0.754	0.197	0,000
	X1.3	0.822	0.197	0,000
	X1.4	0.779	0.197	0,000
	X1.5	0.772	0.197	0,000
	X1.6	0.802	0.197	0,000
	X1.7	0.806	0.197	0,000

Variables	Question Items	Validity		
		Pearson Correlation	r-table	Sig.
Human Resources Strengthening (X2)	X2.1	0.697	0.197	0,000
	X2.2	0.776	0.197	0,000
	X2.3	0.591	0.197	0,000
	X2.4	0.579	0.197	0,000
	X2.5	0.753	0.197	0,000
	X2.6	0.660	0.197	0,000
	X2.7	0.634	0.197	0,000
	X2.8	0.685	0.197	0,000
	X2.9	0.644	0.197	0,000
	X2.10	0.659	0.197	0,000
	X2.11	0.690	0.197	0,000
	X2.12	0.696	0.197	0,000
	X2.13	0.625	0.197	0,000
	X2.14	0.580	0.197	0,000
	X2.15	0.555	0.197	0,000

Variables	Question Items	Validity		
		<i>Pearson Correlation</i>	r-table	Sig.
Communication Strategy (X3)	X3.1	0.653	0.197	0,000
	X3.2	0.701	0.197	0,000
	X3.3	0.790	0.197	0,000
	X3.4	0.738	0.197	0,000
	X3.5	0.763	0.197	0,000
	X3.6	0.759	0.197	0,000
	X3.7	0.720	0.197	0,000
	X3.8	0.775	0.197	0,000
	X3.9	0.801	0.197	0,000
	X3.10	0.763	0.197	0,000
	X3.11	0.720	0.197	0,000
	X3.12	0.835	0.197	0,000
	X3.13	0.782	0.197	0,000
	X3.14	0.807	0.197	0,000
	X3.15	0.699	0.197	0,000
	X3.16	0.641	0.197	0,000
	X3.17	0.650	0.197	0,000
	X3.18	0.642	0.197	0,000
	X3.19	0.659	0.197	0,000
	X3.20	0.704	0.197	0,000
	X3.21	0.701	0.197	0,000
	X3.22	0.629	0.197	0,000
	X3.23	0.599	0.197	0,000

Variables	Question Items	Validity		
		<i>Pearson Correlation</i>	r-table	Sig.
Decent Work (Y)	Y.1	0.600	0.197	0,000
	Y.2	0.517	0.197	0,000
	Y.3	0.748	0.197	0,000
	Y.4	0.635	0.197	0,000
	Y.5	0.571	0.197	0,000
	Y.6	0.539	0.197	0,000
	Y.7	0.672	0.197	0,000
	Y.8	0.744	0.197	0,000
	Y.9	0.694	0.197	0,000
	Y.10	0.742	0.197	0,000
	Y.11	0.598	0.197	0,000
	Y.12	0.701	0.197	0,000
	Y.13	0.432	0.197	0,000
	Y.14	0.689	0.197	0,000
	Y.15	0.721	0.197	0,000
	Y.16	0.694	0.197	0,000
	Y.17	0.719	0.197	0,000
	Y.18	0.620	0.197	0,000
	Y.19	0.668	0.197	0,000
	Y.20	0.719	0.197	0,000

Y.21	0.662	0.197	0,000
Y.22	0.574	0.197	0,000
Y.23	0.633	0.197	0,000
Y.24	0.583	0.197	0,000
Y.25	0.530	0.197	0,000
Y.26	0.471	0.197	0,000
Y.27	0.592	0.197	0,000
Y.28	0.494	0.197	0,000
Y.29	0.567	0.197	0,000

This study contains 4 variables with 74 statement items in 100 research samples, with details per variable as follows:

Variables	Reliability		
	Cronchbach's Alpha	N Item	Information
GIG Economy(X1)	0.889	7	Reliable.
Human Resources Strengthening (X2)	0.898	15	Reliable.
Digital Marketing Strategy (X3)	0.957	23	Reliable.
Decent Work (Y)	0.940	29	Reliable.

Normality test using test *One-Sample-Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test* with the asymp. Sig (2-tailed) test result criteria of more than 0.05 then the data is normal and if the test result finds less than 0.05 then the data is not normal.

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test		
		Unstandardized Residual
N		100
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	.0000000
	Standard Deviation	7.58081145
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.063
	Positive	.045
	Negative	-.063
Test Statistics		.063
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.200c,d

The multicollinearity test can be shown by a VIF value of less than 10 and a tolerance value greater than 0.10, then the data is said to be free of multicollinearity.

Table 4.17 Multicollinearity Test Results

Coefficients ^a		Collinearity Statistics	
Model		Tolerance	VIF
1	<i>GIG Economy</i> (X1) Human Resources Strengthening (X2) Digital Communication Strategy (X3)	.451 .434 .454	2,219 2,302 2,204

A heteroscedasticity test can be concluded if the significance value of the test level is greater than 0.05 indicating that heteroscedasticity does not occur, and if the opposite occurs, it can be concluded that heteroscedasticity occurs.

Table 4.18 Heteroscedasticity Test

Coefficients ^a		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
Model		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	6,697	5,497		1,218	.226
	<i>Gig Economy</i> (X1)	.088	.212	.060	.414	.679
	Human Resources Strengthening (X2)	-.115	.094	-.164	-1.224	.224
	Digital Communication Strategy (X3)	.043	.071	.087	.602	.549

a. Dependent Variable: AbS_RES

The autocorrelation test uses the Durbin Watson (DW) value with the following criteria. Data is said to have autocorrelation if the d value < dL or d value > 4-dL, data is said to have no autocorrelation if dU < d < 4-dU and data is said to have no conclusion if dL < d < dU.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Standard Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.810a	.657	.646	7,698	1,647

Coefficientsa						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	19,424	8,016		2,423	.017
	<i>GIG Economy</i> (X1)	.866	.311	.248	2,786	.006
	Human Resources Strengthening (X2)	.827	.174	.432	4,759	.000
	Digital Communication Strategy (X3)	.266	.104	.226	2,548	.012

Based on the results of the analysis, it can be seen that the Df value in this study is $n-1 = 100 - 1 = 99$, so the t-table value with the df value obtained is 1.984 (at a 5% confidence level) with a significance level of 0.05. Therefore, the regression equation in this study is:

$$Y = 19,424 + 0,866X1 + 0.827 X2 + 0.266X3$$

The F test is used to see to what extent independent variables can influence the dependent variable together.

ANOVA						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	10877.588	3	3625.863	61,181	.000b
	Residual	5689.402	96	59,265		
	Total	16566.990	99			

DISCUSSION

Based on the results of statistical tests, it is proven that the GIG Economy has a positive and significant influence on Decent Work for female workers in supporting SDGs 8 in Mataram City so that the first research hypothesis is accepted. This finding indicates that the existence of the GIG Economy can be one of the driving factors and an important predictor in achieving decent work in the current era which can have an impact on improving the welfare of the community, especially for women in Mataram City who are able to encourage sustainable economic growth. This is in line with the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB). (Darsono et al., 2020). In the attitude towards behavior aspect, the flexibility of time provides opportunities for women to have profitable work opportunities because it provides freedom in managing the workload so that it can directly become a solution to the dual roles they carry and provide a balance between life and work. The subjective norm side is able to increase social acceptance for women both in the family and social environment for being able to participate in earning a living and with the flexibility of time and place of work carried out provides moral support for the obligations of the dual role carried out so that it can be accepted by partners or other family members. And perceived behavioral control, women as GIG Economy workers feel capable and easy to contribute because they only need basic skills in applying simple platforms that do not require high academic degrees or extensive social networks.

Strengthening human resources has a positive and significant impact on decent work. This means that strengthening human resources plays a crucial role in improving decent work, thus accepting the second hypothesis of this study. The statistical test results show a positive value, indicating a directional relationship. This means that improving human resources in Mataram City can increase the opportunities for female workers to obtain decent work. Improving decent work directly supports the sustainable development goals contained in SDGs 8, namely decent work and economic growth. These results align with the theory of human capital, in which Theodore Schultz (1960) stated that human resources are considered a vital asset that can improve organizational performance. Investments made in human resources can increase the productivity and efficiency of an organization comprehensively and sustainably. Communication strategy influence on decent work, so the third hypothesis is accepted. This significant influence indicates that the more effective the digital communication strategy, the higher the level of decent work achievement. Digital communication strategies can enable the dissemination of employment information more widely, evenly, quickly, openly or transparently and are able to increase public awareness in the

context of flexibility, productivity, and equal employment opportunities, especially for female workers in Mataram City. In line with the theory of Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC), which states that an integrated digital communication strategy can convey messages or information consistently and effectively through various digital media. In the context of SDGs 8, through the IMC approach implemented by combining social media, digital campaigns, and educational content, it can strengthen the values of equality, productivity, and economic empowerment for female workers, especially female workers in Mataram City. GIG Economy, strengthening human resources (HR) and digital communication strategies simultaneously influence decent work in supporting sustainable development (SDGs 8) in Mataram City. The results of the study indicate that the three variables have a joint influence on decent work, so that the fourth hypothesis is accepted. Empirically, the results of this study indicate that the three variables together are able to increase the availability, quality and feasibility of work in the digital era, so that the combination of a technology-based flexible work system (GIG Economy), strengthening human resources (HR) and effective digital communication can create an inclusive and equitable work ecosystem. The synergy between the three variables not only expands access to employment, but can strengthen aspects of productivity, equality, and work protection, especially for female workers in Mataram City.

CONCLUSION

The presence and growth of the GIG Economy in Mataram City has a real (significant) important role in improving the quality of decent work for female workers. The higher the participation or intensity of women in the GIG Economy, the greater the opportunity to get work that meets decent standards (fair wages, flexibility, security, and protection). In addition, improving the quality and capacity of Human Resources (HR) for female workers in Mataram City through relevant education and training has a strong impact, in order to improve the quality of work into decent work which shows that investment in women's skills is the main key to ensuring fair wages, job protection, and better career prospects. The implementation of effective digital communication strategies by female workers in Mataram City has a strong impact on improving the quality of work. Skills in utilizing digital media not only open access to new jobs but can also increase efficiency, market reach and wage bargaining power, thus directly supporting the achievement of Sustainable Development Goal 8 (SDGs 8). GIG Economy, Human Resources Strengthening and Digital Communication Strategy simultaneously have a positive and significant impact on decent work in supporting sustainable development (SDGs 8) in Mataram City, so that an integrated combination of job opportunities through GIG Economy, improving the quality of skills and abilities in utilizing digital platforms collectively becomes an effective strategy in encouraging the realization of decent work for female workers in Mataram City and directly supports the successful achievement of SDGs 8 which ultimately directly supports the achievement of Sustainable Development Goal number 8 (SDGs 8).

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